

Resume Based Job Recommendation For Job Seekers

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Abstract— Job portals are beginning to receive a huge volume of resumes in a diverse range of formats and structures from job applicants with various fields of expertise and specialty in many disciplines as a result of the expansion of online recruiting. Consequently, it is necessary to automatically extract unstructured information from these resumes in order to support automatic matching between candidate resumes and relevant job offers as well as to effectively route them to the appropriate occupational categories in order to reduce the amount of work needed to manage and organise them. As a consequence, only those resumes and job postings that fit under a certain skill area will be matched to their appropriate job posts rather than doing a general search of the full domain of resumes and job postings. In this research, we provide a recommendation system for job searchers based on resumes. The system automatically extracts the skills from the Resume and suggests job postings based on the cosine similarity score. In comparison to conventional methods, we get promising accuracy results using the real-world job posting dataset.

Keywords: *Job recommendation systems, job matching, job seeking, and job searching.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The goal of this job recommendation engine was to filter job openings in accordance with the skills and abilities that job searchers had developed. The proposed system gathers both the soft skills and hard talents from the user profile or resume whenever users update their resumes or profiles. The system will then filter the job openings and display them on the website's jobseeker side based on that matching data. In order to achieve this objective, various user activities and user profiles, including job descriptions and applicant CVs, are reviewed. The recommendation method is modelled using TF-IDF and cosine similarity. Knowledge and skills are taken from the entire resume, and after that, the user's skills are matched with job openings on the website. The job entities are then evaluated in accordance with how well-suited they are to the target user, taking into account both the preferences of employers and applicants.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Pradeep Kumar Roy, Sarabjeet Singh Chowdhury, Rocky Bhatia [1] developed a model for intelligent machine learning that suggests a suitable resume for job aspirants to the hour backed by employment recruiters' needs.

Yao Lu, Sandy El Helou, Denis Gillet [2] presented a hybrid, personalized recommender system for job seeking and recruiting websites. In this scenario, a preliminary analysis conducted on a dataset from the production website clearly shows that the system performed best on recommendation precision and user coverage than content-based profile match and collaborative filtering.

Vinay Desai, Dheeraj Bahl, Shreekumar Vibhandik, Isra Fatma[3] created a simple system for making job recommendations where everyone will have an equal chance. Both the industrial side and the job seeker's side benefit greatly from this potential time and financial savings. Additionally, it is a much more effective system because the candidate is given a fair opportunity to demonstrate his talent in the real world.

Jorge Valverde-Rebaza, Ricardo Puma, Paul Bustios, Nathalia C. Silva [4] conducted an empirical study on job recommendation based on jobseeker's skills. They put forth a framework for the task of job recommendations. This framework makes it easier to understand how job recommendations work and permits the use of a variety of text processing and recommendation techniques in accordance with the preferences of the person who designed the job recommender system.

Anushka Agarwal, Dr. Senthilkumar [5] developed a resume recommendation using cosine similarity. In accordance with the verbal job description, they suggested an automatic machine learning model that helped the recruiter recommend the resumes of suitable candidates.

III. METHODOLOGY

The goal of this paper is to develop a recommendation engine that will retrieve a person-fit job based on the skills listed in the job-resume. seeker's The model ought to be capable of identifying suitable jobs that correspond to the job seeker.

Figure 1: Resume Based Job Recommendation System Methodology

The TF-IDF Vectorizer and Cosine-Similarity will be used to recommend person fit jobs. The structure is:

Methodology for Job Recommendations Based on Resumes
The actions that must be taken are as follows:

1. Information Gathering
2. Data Processing
3. Feature Extraction
4. Machine Learning

A. Information Gathering: Jobseekers have structured or unstructured resume, which having details such as skills, knowledge or experience. And also the system contains a job opening dataset which contains the fields such as job description, job title, job id. So two details are necessary for modelling recommendation ie,

- a. Resume of the jobseeker: From the resume we need to extract skills from experience and projects. So we are using SkillNer a python package to collect the skill key words from the unstructured resume.

SkillNer is an NLP module to automatically Extract skills and certifications from unstructured job postings, texts, and applicant's resumes. Skillner uses EMSI database (an open source skill database) as a knowledge base linker to prevent skill duplications.

- b. Job vacancy dataset: Load the job opening dataset in google colab notebook. The dataset should contain the fields like job title, job description, job requirements, company name.

B. Data Processing: This is the step that is done in every machine learning method. This process includes data cleaning and data reduction. This all are done to make the data more effective. The data can be processed to make our model more accurate. So that the recommendation will be more precise and accurate.

- I. **Data Cleaning** – Data cleaning is done first. Eliminating the undesirable entries. The dataset can also be cleaned up by removing the noisy and missing data.
- II. **Removing Stop words** – The stop words are eliminated from the datasets for job openings. These are the ones that appear the most frequently yet aren't given much weight in the text. This can be done to increase the model's accuracy.

C. Feature Extraction: Text processing uses feature extraction, where words in the text stand in for distinct, categorical features. How can we create an algorithm-ready form of encoding for such data? The process of converting textual data into actual valued vectors is referred to as feature extraction. Bag of Words is among the simplest methods for numerically representing text.

Bag of Words (BOW): We create a list of distinct words from the corpus of text that we refer to as vocabulary. Then, each word in each sentence or document can be represented as a vector, with 1 denoting its presence in the vocabulary and 0 denoting its absence. The number of times a word appears in a document can be counted as another representation. The Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) technique is the most widely used method.

Term Frequency (TF) = (Number of times term t appears in a document) / (Number of terms in the document)

Inverse Document Frequency (IDF) = $\log(N/n)$,

n is the number of documents a term t has appeared in, and N is the total number of documents. An uncommon word has a high IDF, whereas a frequent word is more likely to have a low IDF. Words that are distinct are highlighted as a result.

We calculate a term's TF-IDF value as = $TF * IDF$.

D. Machine Learning:

This is used to recommend the jobs. A person fit recommender system to find out the suitable jobs for jobseekers using content-based filtering. Similarity metrics in this system is cosine similarity.

1. Recommendation Algorithms

Content-based filtering (CBF) compares an item's features to a user preference profile in an abstract way. In other words, this algorithm looks for items that are comparable to past user favorites. It is frequently used for information retrieval (IR). However, because it can be challenging to extract item attributes and sometimes obtain user preferences, it performs poorly in multimedia fields like music or movie recommendation.

2. Similarity Calculation Methods

Cosine Similarity: Cosine similarity measures the degree of similarity between two N-dimensional vectors by comparing their cosine values. It's a popular tool for information retrieval (IR).

$$\text{cosine similarity} = S_C(A, B) := \cos(\theta) = \frac{A \cdot B}{\|A\| \|B\|} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n A_i B_i}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n A_i^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n B_i^2}}$$

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

In this system we use cosine similarity to find the similarity between the job title and skills from the resume and outputs the most similar jobs to the jobseeker.

Using google colab lets implement our system, first create a new project then upload a sample resume .Take job opening dataset from kaggle.com. Load the dataset to the corresponding folder.

A. Install and Import the necessary libraries.

```
import PyPDF2
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
%matplotlib inline
import spacy
nlp = spacy.load('en_core_web_lg')
from spacy.matcher import PhraseMatcher
from skillNer.general_params import SKILL_DB
from skillNer.skill_extractor_class import SkillExtractor
from google.colab import drive
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import difflib
from sklearn.feature_extraction.text import TfidfVectorizer
from sklearn.metrics.pairwise import cosine_similarity
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns
```

B. Extract the skills from the resume using skillner. skillExtractor function is used where nlp, skills_db, phraseMatcher are the attributes.is the object loaded from spacy and

```
skill_extractor = SkillExtractor(nlp, SKILL_DB, PhraseMatcher)
annotations = skill_extractor.annotate(text)
allresult = annotations['results']
allresult.keys()
def recursive_items(allresult):
    for key, value in allresult.items():
        if type(value) is dict:
            yield (key, value)
            yield from recursive_items(value)
        else:
            yield (key, value)

# a = {'a': {1: {1: 2, 3: 4}, 2: {5: 6}}}}

for key, value in recursive_items(allresult):
    print(key, value)
fullmatches = allresult['full_matches']
ngrams_scored = allresult['ngram_scored']
```

C. Preprocessing job opening dataset and examining the output

```
job_data = pd.read_csv('/content/jobposts(1).csv')
job_data = job_data.fillna("")
job_data.head()
```

index	Job Title	Job Description	Company Name
0	0.0 Senior Data Scientist	ABOUT HOPPER\n\nAt Hopper, we're on a mission ...	Hopper\n3.5
1	1.0 Data Scientist, Product Analytics	At Noon, we use scientifically proven methods ...	Noon US\n4.5
2	2.0 Data Science Manager	Decode_M\n\nhttps://www.decode-m.com/\n\nData ...	Decode_M
3	3.0 Data Analyst	Sapphire Digital seeks a dynamic and driven mi...	Sapphire Digital\n3.4
4	4.0 Director, Data Science	Director, Data Science - (200637)\n\nDescription...	United Entertainment Group\n3.4

D. Apply TF_IDF transformation to get two real valued vectors of Job title from job opening dataset and skills from resume.

```
def TFIDF(scraped_data, cv):
    tfidf_vectorizer = TfidfVectorizer(stop_words='english')

    # TF-IDF Scraped data
    tfidf_jobid = tfidf_vectorizer.fit_transform(scraped_data)

    # TF-IDF CV
    user_tfidf = tfidf_vectorizer.transform(cv)

    # Using cosine_similarity on (Scraped data) & (CV)
    cos_similarity_tfidf = map(lambda x: cosine_similarity(user_tfidf,x),tfidf_jobid)

    output2 = list(cos_similarity_tfidf)
    return output2

output2 = TFIDF(job_data['Job Title'], df2['All'])
output2
```

E. Get the recommendation function and calling the function

```
def get_recommendation(top, df_all, scores):  
    recommendation = pd.DataFrame(columns = ['Job Title', 'Job Description', 'Company Name', 'score'])  
    count = 0  
    for i in top:  
  
        recommendation.at[count, 'Job Title'] = job_data['Job Title'][i]  
        recommendation.at[count, 'Job Description'] = job_data['Job Description'][i]  
        recommendation.at[count, 'Company Name'] = job_data['Company Name'][i]  
        recommendation.at[count, 'score'] = scores[count]  
        count += 1  
    return recommendation
```

```
top = sorted(range(len(output2)), key=lambda i: output2[i], reverse=True)[:50]  
list_scores = [output2[i][0][0] for i in top]  
TF=get_recommendation(top,job_data, list_scores)  
TF
```

V. RESULTS

The result is generated after the dataset and skillset is passed to the TF_IDF vectorizer and cosine similarity. The most similar hundred job openings are recommended to the job seekers. And also g

VI. CONCLUSION

In this research report, we presented a system for recommending jobs to job seekers based on their available skill sets as listed on their resumes. Here, cosine similarity is used as the similarity vector, and TF IDF vectorization is employed for transformation. Additionally, scores are computed based on similarity.

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